

THE PERCEIVED READING PERFORMANCE, THE CHALLENGES, AND THE ENGLISH ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE SIX PUPILS IN PILAR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the perceived reading performance, challenges and English achievement of Grade Six pupils in Pilar District for the School Year 2022-2023. It further examined the relationship between reading performance and English achievement and challenges encountered in teaching reading. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed involving the public elementary school teachers from the 21 schools in Pilar District, Bohol. Each teacher has approximately 25-35 pupils per classroom with the total of 412 Grade six pupils within the district. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) and analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, weighted mean, and chi-square test. Findings revealed that learners demonstrated a high-level reading performance, with alphabet knowledge rated very high while other domains such as word recognition, phonological awareness, comprehension, and fluency were rated high. English achievement was generally satisfactory. A significant positive relationship was found between reading performance and English achievement, while no significant relationship was found between English achievement and teaching challenges. Teachers reported challenges primarily related to lack of parental support and limited instructional resources. The findings suggest that improving reading performance can enhance learners' English achievement.

Keywords: *Reading Performance, English Achievement, Reading Challenges, Elementary Learners, Philippine Informal Reading Inventory, Pilar District*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a fundamental skill essential for learners' academic success and overall development (Cimmiyotti,2013; Duke & Pearson,2002). However, many Filipino learners continue to face difficulties in reading, as reflected in national and international assessments such as the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM, 2019) and the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018), where the Philippines ranked among the lowest in reading proficiency (Bernardo et al.,2022). These results highlight the urgency of strengthening literacy instruction in basic education. The Department of Education has implemented programs such as the DepEd Order No. 14, s.2018, Policy on the Administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) as support on DepEd Flagship Program Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) to address literacy gaps (Department of Education, 2019). Despite these initiatives, many learners remain at instructional and frustration levels, particularly in comprehension (Tizon, 2013). Reading performance is influenced by multiple factors, including phonological awareness, vocabulary, fluency, and environmental support such as parental involvement (Piasta & Wagner, 2020; Shahzad et al.,2020).

Anchored on Goodman's Psycholinguistic Model of Reading (Goodman,1967) and Rumelhart's Schema Theory (Rumelhart,1977), this study views reading as an active process where learners construct meaning through interaction with text and prior knowledge. Given the observed reading difficulties among Grade Six pupils in Pilar District, this study was conducted to examine their reading performance, English achievement, and the challenges encountered in teaching reading, as well as to determine the relationships among these variables.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to determine the perceived reading performance, challenges and the English achievement of grade six pupils in Pilar District for the school year 2022-2023. The outputs of the study would serve as the basis for a proposed enhancement program.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading performance of grade six pupils in Pilar District in terms of:
 - 1.1 alphabet knowledge;
 - 1.2 word recognition;
 - 1.3 phonological awareness;
 - 1.4 comprehension; and
 - 1.5 fluency?
2. What is the English achievement of Grade six pupils in Pilar District?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of reading performance and English achievement?
4. What are the challenges encountered in teaching reading?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the English achievement of the pupils and the challenges encountered in teaching reading?

6. Through evident findings, what enhancement program can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents of the study were public elementary school teachers from the 21 schools in Pilar District, Bohol. Each teacher handled approximately 25-35 pupils per classroom with the total of 412 Grade six pupils across the district. Teachers were chosen through purposive sampling because they are the ones who are able to observe their pupils' learning achievement based on the objectives given in the study. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of three parts: the first part consisted of questions that determined the level of reading performance in terms of alphabet knowledge, phonic awareness, word-recognition, fluency, and comprehension. Second section was the English achievement of grade six pupils in Pilar District. The part 1 and 2 of the questionnaire was based on standardized Phil-IRI. It was collected back on the spot to avoid any type of bias that might arise as a result of filling the answers to the questionnaire. Third section was the challenges encountered by the respondents in teaching reading. The part 3 of the questionnaire was based on a review of previous studies' literature. To test the validity of the questionnaire the researcher underwent validation and pilot testing prior to administration. Permission to conduct the study was secured from relevant authorities, and ethical standards such as voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent were strictly observed. Data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, weighted mean, and chi-square test to determine relationships between variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings revealed that Grade Six learners demonstrated a generally high level of reading performance, with an overall mean of 3.88. Alphabet knowledge was rated very high, indicating strong foundational skills, while word recognition, phonological awareness, comprehension, and fluency were rated high, suggesting areas that still require improvement. Among these, fluency obtained the lowest mean, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. In terms of English achievement, most learners obtained satisfactory ratings, indicating that while learners meet minimum academic expectations, there is still room for improvement toward higher achievement level.

Correlation analysis showed a significant positive relationship between reading performance and English achievement, implying that improvements in reading skills contribute to better academic performance in English. The finding supports existing literature emphasizing the role of reading proficiency in academic success. However, no significant relationship was found between English achievement and challenges encountered in teaching reading. Despite this, teachers reported encountering several challenges, particularly lack of parental support, limited instructional materials, and insufficient training opportunities. These findings suggest that while such challenges exist, they may not be directly influence learners' English achievement, indicating the

presence of other contributing factors such as learner motivation and instructional practice.

Conclusions

Reading performance significantly influences the English achievement of Grade Six pupils, with stronger reading skills leading to better academic outcomes. While learners demonstrate strong foundational skills, improvements are needed in higher-level reading domains such as fluency and comprehension. Although teachers encounter challenges in teaching reading, these do not significantly affect learners' English achievement. Strengthening reading instruction and support systems remains essential in improving learners' overall academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of study, the following are proposed:

1. Teachers may include domains such as word recognition, phonological awareness, comprehension, and fluency can be improved by a formalized policy-oriented intervention program that is tailored to the improvement of identified at-risk readers along those domains.
2. School heads may initiate dialogues with their teachers to pinpoint critical areas for improvement. This way, the learners will be informed of the areas for improvement and be able to cope further to improve their academic standing in the English class.
3. District supervisors may initiate mitigation measures to address the challenges experienced by teachers by organizing Parent and Teacher consultation to solicit participation from the latter in monitoring and tracking the student's reading habits and progress especially during the release of pupils' cards.
4. School heads may implement comprehensive and more inclusive reading programs and advocacies in the school setting to integrate the culture of reading and encourage students to bring about positive attitude in reading, since the students' level of reading performance was proven to correlate significantly with their achievement in an English class.
5. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in other school districts and other at-risk readers in other grade levels to come up with wider and more generalizable findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that all ethical standards were strictly followed throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were given the freedom to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained, and all data gathered were treated in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The well-being of participants was safeguarded at all times and no harm was inflicted during the process of data collection. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly citing all sources, and the interpretation of the findings was carried out objectively without any bias. The results of the study were used

solely for research purposes. Furthermore, no artificial intelligence tools were used in generating or analyzing the data. Any use of digital tools was limited only to language editing for clarity and did not influence the content, analysis, interpretation, or findings of the study, thereby ensuring the integrity, originality, and the authenticity of the research.

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